

Emotional Exhaustion and Turnover Intention Among Employees: An Empirical Perspective

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ABSTRACT

There is a lack of empirical studies on the relationship between emotional exhaustion and turnover intention from various industry perspectives. The current study attempts to review emotional exhaustion and its effect on turnover intention among the employees of various industries. A review of literature was conducted by using online databases such as Sage, ScienceDirect and Elsevier. Sixty (60) journal articles and conference proceedings on the subject matter were published between 1966 - 2021 and were reviewed from various sectors and industries such as airline, healthcare, customer services, manufacturing, insurance, ICT, human services, hospitality, and education industry, in which most articles were adopting quantitative research approaches. Previous studies highlighted the presence of a strong correlation between emotional exhaustion and turnover intention. Employees are entreated to challenging workloads and regularly burdened with boundless yet demanding working environment; thus, those factors would lead the employees to own the intention to quit their jobs, those factors were also the reasons which have caused opposing

effect on employees work efficiency and presentation, job gratification and pledge to their organization. Recommendations from the past studies suggested that important practices can be utilized to solve emotional exhaustion among employees and to reduce the turnover intention.

Keywords: *Sustainable Organization; Turnover Intention; Emotional Exhaustion; Organizational Psychology, Sustainability*

INTRODUCTION

Employees in various industries increasingly experience emotional exhaustion (EE) due to challenging workloads and demanding working environments. Emotional exhaustion means the feeling of being tired and overly extended emotionally through interactions with others (Jyoti, Rani & Gandotra, 2015; Shirom, 2005; Yavas, Babakus & Karatepe, 2008). Emotional exhaustion manifests when an individual is morbidly exhausted due to interpersonal relationships and working conditions (Wu & Hu, 2009). Emotional exhaustion elevates the feeling of hardship and lowers self-esteem, leading to a negative mindset towards customers, organization, work, and themselves (Cordes & Dougherty, 1993; Ogungbamila, 2014) to decrease the job satisfaction (Scanlan & Still, 2019) and emotional exhaustion (Mangi & Jalbani, 2013).

There are a few adverse impacts derived from the incidence of emotional exhaustion in which it comprehends straight effects such as deprived job productivity (Davidson, Timo & Wang, 2010; Varghese & Kumar, 2019) and work engagement (Ivanovic, Ivancevic & Maricic, 2020). According to Baba, Tourigny, Wang and Liu (2009), individuals who are

emotionally exhausted are more likely to have their success diminished and their capacity reduced in response to work demands. Hence, this may lead to higher emotional exhaustion and thus affects its performance.

A high level of emotional exhaustion can prompt turnover intention (Sawyer, Srinivas, & Wang, 2009; Yavas et al., 2008). Meeusen, Van Dam, Brown-Mahoney, Zundert, Van Zundert and Knape (2011) defined turnover intention as a likelihood or having perceiving thought of leaving the current job. In simple words, employees feel about leaving or quitting their job (Kaur, 2013). The impacts of emotional exhaustion on turnover intentions will likely come with some adverse outcomes, for example, induced sick leaves, increased employee stress levels, and higher turnover rates (Hatzinikolakis & Crossman, 2010). High turnover rates among employees lead to adverse effects on the organization, such as decreased productivity and poor work performance. In a study by (Waldman, Kelly, Arora & Smith, 2004), high turnover in health care is very costly, with an estimated cost of >5% of an organization's budget expense. Shockingly, as reported by a previous study, high turnover among the registered nurses could result in the closure of hospital units, which could further lead to delaying treatment and subsequently endanger patients' health, safety, and well-being (Bae, Mark, & Fried, 2010).

Emotional exhaustion is one of the critical determinants of burnout and turnover intention. It is a crucial precursor of actual turnover as being experienced by health care practitioners (Knudsen, Ducharme & Roman, 2006; Lagerlund, Sharp, Lindqvist & Runesdotter, 2015). Thus, it is vital to be aware of the connections between emotional exhaustion (EE) and turnover intention (TI) among employees in the organization.

Emotional Exhaustion (EE) and Turnover Intention (TI)

Research investigating emotional exhaustion and turnover intention was carried out in western and eastern countries (*Table 1*). Western countries included are Saudi Arabia, India, South African, Northern Cyprus, Netherlands, United States, Europe, Iran, and Pakistan, while eastern countries included China, Taiwan, and Korea. These studies were carried out among employees of different industries such as the service industry, education industry, insurance industry, ICT industry, addiction treatment organization, hospitality industry, human service industry, customer service industry, mental health care organization, and airline industry.

Table 1
Summary of Studies on the Relationship between Emotional Exhaustion and Turnover Intention from various countries, industries, and populations

Sources	Country	Industry	Population	Findings
Sabine, G., Wilmar, S., and Jan De Jonge (1998)	Netherlands	Mental Health Care Organization	Mental health care professionals	No significant relationship between EE and TI
Babakus, E., Cravens, D.W., Johnston, M., and Moncrief	United States	International Services Organization	Salesperson	Strong positive relationship between EE and TI

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(1999)

Knudsen et al. (2006)	United States	Therapeutic Communities	Therapeutic Counselor	Positive correlation between EE and TI
Ducharme, L. J., Knudsen, H. K., & Roman, P. M. (2008)	United States	Addiction treatment organizations	Administrators of substance	Positive association between EE and TI
Ducharme et al. (2008)	United States	Human services industry	Counselors of treatment facilities	EE is positively correlated to TI
Karatepe and Karatepe (2010)	Northern Cyprus	Hospitality industry	Front-line employees	Negative association between EE and TI
Du Plooy & Roodt (2010)	South African	ICT industry	Employees in ICT sector company	EE is positively related to TI

Rehman (2012)	Pakistan	Customer Service Industry	Customer service representatives	EE is positively related to TI
Qin, L., Xu, S., and Ji, H. (2012)	China	Hotel Industry	Chinese Hotel employees	A positive influence of EE on TI
Arshadi & Shahbazi (2013)	Iran	Industrial Organization	Industrial male workers	EE has positive relationship with TI
Shih-Tze Wang (2014)	Taiwan	Service industry	Frontline worker in restaurant	EE is significantly related to TI
Fila (2014)	Europe	Insurance industry	Employees from national insurance company	EE was positively related to TI
Cho, J. E., Choi, H. C., and Lee, W. J. (2014)	Korea	Airline Industry	Customer Contact Employee	EE positively related to TI
Jyoti et al. (2015)	India	Education industry	Teachers in colleges	EE positively effects on TI

Seongho, K., Hur, W. M. and Park, K. D. (2015)	China	Chinese Service Industry	Departmental Store Salesperson	EE positively related on TI
Nazer (2015)	Saudi Arabia	Education industry	Faculty member in university	EE is positively related to TI

Note. Developed for research.

There is a positive and significant relationship between emotional exhaustion and turnover intention based on previous research findings among most western countries and eastern countries. This is also supported by many previous studies which revealed that emotional exhaustion is significantly related to turnover intention (Maslach & Jackson, 1986; Wright, & Cropanzano, 1998; Yavas et al., 2008).

Emotional exhaustion indicates a person's stress reaction to social demands at the workplace (Paulsen, Callan, Grice, Rooney, Gallois, Jones, Jimmieson & Bordia, 2005), that lead to many problems such as impacts on the feelings of disability and self-esteem decline of an individual, which results in a negative attitude toward customers, organization, jobs, and themselves (Cordes & Dougherty, 1993; Ogungbamila, Balogun, Ogungbamila & Oladele, 2014). Besides that, emotional exhaustion causes a lack of energy and depletion of an individual's emotional resources (Karl & Peluchette, 2006) and the job is emotional demands, shiftwork and work-home interference were associated with the exhaustion component of burnout (Scanlan & Still, 2019). This impact will contribute to the Increased rate of exhaustion and result in a higher turnover

rate (Herington et al., 2006). It should be noted that there was a study in the Netherlands among mental health care professionals which reported no significant relationship between emotional exhaustion and turnover intention; This may be due to most of the experienced workers were relatively more vulnerable and could cope with emotional exhaustion while able to reduce the choice to quit (Knani & Fournier, 2013).

However, one research conducted in Northern Cyprus stated that there is a significant negative correlation between emotional exhaustion and turnover intention. In addition, only one industry, the hospitality industry, indicated that emotional exhaustion was negatively related to turnover intention. One of the possible reasons for the negative relationship is the work experiences, as longer-term staff may have gathered a lot of work experience to deal with emotionally exhausting problems. Thus, the emotional exhaustion phenomenon among hospitality employees is not positively related to turnover intention, particularly among frontline employees (Karatepe & Karatepe, 2010). This is supported by the recent study, Ahmad, Syed Faozi Barakbah and Majdi (2021). They found that the level of burnout among hotel employees is moderately associated with their turnover intention. It is noted that the management must help reduce unnecessary burden and stress that could negatively affect employees' level of commitment.

Most of the studies reported that highly committed employees will always positively impact the organization, such as high productivity and high performance. Hence, most of the organizations' managers or superiors concentrate on the commitment relationship between employees and the organization (Fu, Bolander & Jones, 2009). For instance, a manager is always focused on what and how the employees can contribute more to the organization to have better financial returns instead of looking into the employees' emotions during

working time; this will cause emotional exhaustion among the employees, which will result in the rise of intention to quit within the organization; This is supported by Herington, Johnson and Scott (2006) who mentioned that most of the organizations that are not paying close attention in developing organization-employee relationship would have higher employees' intention to quit as the employees' emotional state is not being taken care of when they are working. Therefore, employees' emotional exhaustion and turnover intentions are likely to arise due to the organization's ignorance towards the employee's physical and mental health while still continuously requesting the employees to commit good productivity and performance to the organization. In other words, conflict with superiors and poor supervision are related to emotional exhaustion and lead to job dissatisfaction among employees and turnover intention (Golembiewski, Bordeau, Muszenrider, & Luo, 1966; Maslach, Jackson & Leiter, 1996).

Past researchers also revealed that staff issues such as excessive administration and incorporation between staff would influence the stress level of the employees (Rothman, Van Der Colff, & Rothman, 2006; Tummers, Janssen, Landeweerd & Houkes, 2001). Past studies proved that insufficient social support to the employees would lead to emotional exhaustion (Fatma, Yunus & Esengul, 2014). A stressful working environment will negatively affect the organization, such as the intention to quit the organization and decrease job productivity. In short, employees who work in an enjoyable atmosphere can contribute quality outcomes compared to those who work in a stressful environment.

Overcoming Emotional Exhaustion and Turnover Intention

Previous studies have proven that emotional exhaustion is significantly associated with several job-related consequences

such as voluntary turnover among staff (Maslach & Jackson, 1986; Wright & Cropanzano, 2000), job performance (Wright & Cropanzano, 2000), and turnover intentions (Yavas et al., 2008). In other words, emotional exhaustion is a predictor for employees' withdrawal attitudes from the organization (Arshadi & Shahbazi, 2013). Thus, management should consider and express concern on approaches towards launching, executing, and appraising a set of excellent human resources practices that can be applied to reduce employees' emotional exhaustion and turnover intention. Employers should be aware of the possible types of emotional exhaustion which might manifest among their employees and take appropriate initiatives to lower the influence of emotional exhaustion, which eventually affects organizational performance (Yusoff, Khan & Azam, 2013), and plan and pre plan their employees' works much earlier to increase work efficiency.

In addition, management may empower the staff as this could ensure engagement and commitment among the employees. Thus, tempting the workers to feel like they are part of the organization will make them passionately devoted and have a sense of belonging. Extra executive reflections may include subordinate and tertiary reactions to work stress to lessen mental tension and undesirable turnover. Job design is initially referred to as the customary occasions and constrictions organized into consigned jobs and tasks that will affect how a worker achieves and experiences the organization effort (Hackman & Oldham, 1976).

Another approach to overcome emotional exhaustion is through subordinate interferences, which emphasize the quick detection and supervision of stress by alertness from the supervisors. Furthermore, to cultivate stress prevention awareness, an individual should go through training and educational activities and support from the management to organize recreation

practices and lifestyle alteration activities for employees (Cooper & Cartwright, 1997; Wang & Wang, 2020). On top of that, a study among Chinese hotel employees in China reported that the managers should frequently be alerted with regards to their employees' emotional exhaustion condition and should provide timely guidance and support whenever the employees are found to be fatigued (Qin et al., 2012). This study's analytical contribution, which could minimize worker turnover, results from good human resources practices within the organization. From the other perspective of Vietnamese civil service employees' work exhaustion and job satisfaction point of view, the adverse effects of social support, organizational support and job motivation on work exhaustion are insignificant (Nguyen, Thi Sa Do, & Tan Mai, 2020; Giao, Vuong, Huan, Tushar & Quan, 2020).

From the perspective of human resources mainly related to recruitment and selection procedures, the hotel managers should select potential employees who possess a strong emotion of regulation ability that enable them to minimize the occurrences of emotional exhaustion (Qin et al., 2012).

On the other hand, as suggested by (Knudsen et al., 2006), managers need to listen to their staffs' opinions and make decisions wisely and address problems through social interaction, which potentially leads to the reduction of emotional exhaustion experience among the employees and turnover intention. This supported by Elci, Yildiz and Erdilek Karabay (2018) and Fu, Shen and Wei (2018) suggested that subjective vitality and supervisor support are necessary. The recommendations of the strategies mentioned earlier apply to various industries to assist in organization engagement and commitment among the employees in overcoming emotional exhaustion and turnover intention.

Towards Organizational Sustainability in the organization - Managing Emotional Exhaustion

The association between sustainability and workplaces in any organization represents a current articulated grand challenge for human resource development and employee productivity, which calls for integrated inquiries, commented by Brandi, Collin and Lemmetty (2022). This is supported by the U.S. Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) where it recognizes that new strategies are needed and to be complied to ensure that all workers return home safe, sound, and healthy from a day on the job. Sustainability at the workplace encompasses burnout prevention and reducing turnover intention, among others (Van der Heijden et al., 2019). Additionally, Tur-Porcar, Roig-Tierno and Llorca Mestre (2018) found that social and emotional factors are integral in fostering and maintaining sustainability in an organization while sustainability at the workplace has the potential to affect many aspects of organization, including employee productivity.

The surge of research in recent years offering evidence for the importance of emotion factor in organizational sustainability is an indicator that organizations are moving towards human resource management that considers psychological and social wellbeing of their employees. Hitherto, Oborina (2021) in Yusof, Isa and Nee (2022) suggested that human beings who have been identified as organizational assets should participate in a prepared, observable, rational, and competent manner to further the organization's vision, mission, and goals. They are suggesting that it is time to agree on a more inclusive definition of total well-being at work to inspire research on how to optimize the ideal state of employees that predicts significant organizational outcomes.

This shift of organizational practice gave rise to Socially Responsible Human Resource Management (SRHRM), which is an organizational practice directed towards their employees as part of their corporate social responsibility (Jonathan et al., 2020). Good employee-centered human resource practices and a healthy and sustainable work environment contribute to increased productivity. Hence, a workforce's well-being and motivation are promoted through sustainable practices (Smith, 2002).

CONCLUSION

This study focuses on the connection between emotional exhaustion and turnover intention among employees of various industries. Past studies evidenced that emotional exhaustion and turnover intention are significantly related in western and eastern contexts. The authors (Maslach & Jackson, 1981) stated that as the employees' emotional resources are depleted, the workers will feel that they can no longer commit themselves at a psychological level. Thus, individuals who are exhausted, lack energy, and focus mind drop, the persistence of such feelings becomes chronic, and prolonged-lasting are experiencing emotional exhaustion. The verdict here is that these symptoms will cause higher intention to quit the jobs among the employees, regardless of any industries or countries origin.

Recommendations

The recommendations from previous studies can help decrease emotional exhaustion and consequently, overcome the employees' turnover intention. For instance, the association of bond approaches; develop rewards schemes, good human resources practices, job design, and organizational commitment. Recommendation by authors like Rusdi, Mohd.

Nasir, Baharuddin and Lateh (2021) suggested that intervention efforts and services aimed at reducing academic burnout could be effective. Additionally, authors like Ahmad et al. (2021) in their study suggested that the condition of work, work scheduling and the matching of jobs with the employees' capabilities had to be considered to minimize the burnout problems. These recommendations are vital for various industries to overcome the turnover intention of employees as the employees will gain confidence and support from these approaches. As such, the employees will feel that they have the feeling of engagement with the organization and thus decrease having the thought of leaving the current job.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This report is the authors' original work, and no conflict of interest exists between the authors.

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